

Evaluation of Learning Outcome at the Tertiary Education Level in Nigeria

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ABSTRACT

Evaluation is a very important aspect in teaching and learning process, for it is the major tool which helps to assess the quality of teaching and learning respectively. Hence, this paper has looked at the evaluation process adopted by tertiary institutions in Nigeria, using scores of forty students in a statistics course from the department of Mathematics and Statistics of Enugu State University of Science and Technology. Analysis revealed students' poor performance with skewness value, ranging from -1.1 to -0.51. Further analysis revealed that the poor performance may not be blamed on the teacher rather on the students. However, effective evaluation could be achieved by employing the use of some fundamental statistical tools which shows some details concerning the shape and distribution of the result obtained in any examination. This in turn will help to improve teachers/students performances.

Keyword: Examination, Evaluation, Learning, Performance and Teaching

INTRODUCTION

Every learning process has its objectives, which are usually assessed through evaluation to determine how well these objectives have been achieved at the end of the program. To carry out evaluations, there should be bases set aside by way of examination or assessment, which helps the teacher/instructor to determine the extent to which the stated objectives have been achieved. In other words, the primary goal of any exam should be to accurately assess students' learning output. Often times, teachers are faced with the following questions while discharging their duties; are the students really learning what I am teaching? How well do they understand the key concepts I am focusing on? Can they apply what they have learnt in new contexts? What can I do better or differently to help them develop the skills and knowledge they need, to be effective in the course, in subsequent courses, and in their field of endeavour. Some of these questions could readily be answered through evaluation of the program in question. Evaluation process in tertiary institutions in Nigeria has been a thing of great concern. Current evaluation method adopted in many institutions in Nigeria lacks some specific context, description and information about how the students' scores are spread along the normal curve which could help the teacher assess the quality of his/her teaching. This process has been characterized by a lot of challenges ranging from incorrect computation of results either in favour or against the students, improper approximation of points leading to wrong grade level to complete absence of

evaluation. Time pressures may also hinder teachers from thoroughly evaluating whether academic practice is as effective and efficient as it might be, and also, from bringing about the changes which would achieve this end [2].

Any process that will be devoid of these anomalies will be a welcome development in the Tertiary institutions in Nigeria. It has been observed that teachers vary in their method of test administration enough to significantly influence students' scores in the tests [3]. Teacher behaviors that influences the student scores include, providing additional instruction, rewording the instructions for clarity and answering question that arise during the test period. These variations are generally dismissed as measurement errors, though they support the preference for using individually administered achievement test by trained psychometricians when feasible. The ultimate goal of any teacher should be to build towards a standard evaluation process which will tell if the objective(s) of learning process has been achieved or not based on the outcome of the evaluation. Steve et al. [1] was of the view that being able to ascertain the quality of a learning module helps to ensure the highest return-on-investment and perpetuates a positive perception of the value of online learning. Evaluation of tradition classroom method or online teaching should be able to achieve each stated objective[2]. Therefore any evaluation method which cannot clearly display all the components of

evaluation result may not be helpful in improving teacher delivery ability and students' learning capability.

The outcome of any assessment evaluation process may not be complete until it is used to improve on either teaching or learning process. For this, teachers in tertiary institution must reflect on findings, deliberate about their meaning and implications, and use new insights to design more effective teaching approaches, curriculum, and policies to support students' learning and success. Assessment/evaluation should not be only seen as a way of satisfying program requirement but as a way of measuring the extent to which objectives of the program has been satisfied to achieve the set objective. Assessment/evaluation should follow a cyclical pattern which could be represented as: stating a clear objective, assessing/evaluating the extent to which the objective has been achieved, and using the outcome of the evaluation to make changes which, in turn, become the focus for a next phase of

assessment and improvement. At its best, assessment reflects the ethic of inquiry that informs academic life more broadly, thereby bringing teacher's habits and values as researchers and scholars to their work as educators and to their students' learning.

METHODOLOGY

Taking a case study of forty students in the department of Industrial Mathematics/ Applied Statistics in Enugu state university of science and technology, scores of 40 students who took four different courses in Statistics (STA 451, STA 341, STA 442, and STA 443) under the same teacher were considered. STA 451, STA 442, and STA 443 are fourth year courses while STA 341 is a third year course. The results are published using a six point scale as follows; 70 and above = A, 60-69 =B, 50-59 =C, 45-59 =D, 40-44= E and 0-39 =F. The results are as presented in table1 below.

Table 1 Scores of 40 Students in Statistics courses

STA 451	STA 443	STA 341	STA 442
34.00	34.00	43.00	52.00
45.00	58.00	38.00	58.00
48.00	48.00	41.00	60.00
40.00	50.00	70.00	67.00
40.00	45.00	48.00	60.00
42.00	53.00	53.00	68.00
46.00	54.00	64.00	64.00
40.00	48.00	46.00	61.00
45.00	60.00	36.00	58.00
40.00	57.00	50.00	77.00
50.00	60.00	65.00	66.00
48.00	46.00	47.00	84.00
29.00	50.00	50.00	37.00
41.00	66.00	46.00	66.00
33.00	46.00	48.00	62.00
50.00	77.00	42.00	74.00
45.00	50.00	41.00	47.00
20.00	52.00	56.00	71.00
50.00	52.00	30.00	75.00
45.00	70.00	36.00	66.00
34.00	33.00	72.00	66.00
33.00	55.00	47.00	67.00
31.00	58.00	65.00	20.00
45.00	72.00	38.00	51.00
30.00	28.00	51.00	68.00
33.00	43.00	28.00	78.00
45.00	60.00	60.00	72.00
36.00	56.00	40.00	63.00
46.00	54.00	71.00	55.00
55.00	60.00	73.00	68.00
52.00	53.00	64.00	38.00
45.00	51.00	51.00	57.00
30.00	57.00	61.00	71.00
41.00	25.00	62.00	47.00

44.00	48.00	46.00	64.00
49.00	57.00	40.00	62.00
40.00	40.00	25.00	48.00
52.00	66.00	51.00	60.00
39.00	24.00	37.00	67.00
33.00	54.00	47.00	45.00

Table 2 Summary of grades for STA 45

A	B	C	D	E	F	TOTAL
-	-	6	12	9	13	40

Table3 Summary of grades for STA 443

A	B	C	D	E	F	TOTAL
3	6	18	6	2	5	40

Table 4 Summary of grades for STA 341

A	B	C	D	E	F	TOTAL
4	7	7	8	6	8	40

Table 5 Summary of grades for STA 442

A	B	C	D	E	F	TOTAL
8	19	6	4	-	3	40

From tables 2, 3, 4 and 5, the summary of the grades obtained from these courses were as presented. These results lack some characteristics which could be used to assess its overall quality for improvement on both the teacher and the students. However; using SPSS package, the quality of the results were measured by determining the distribution of the scores using their skewness, Skewness value of zero is considered to give a desirable result since it indicates that the result follows a normal distribution. From the analysis result, it was observed that the distribution of the students' score does not follow a normal curve. STA 451, STA 442 and STA 443 have skewness values of -0.509, -1.091 and -0.497 respectively indicating that the scores were skewed to the left but STA 341 has skewness value of 0.227 showing that the scores were skewed to the right although it is close to zero which could be said to be a better result than the result of the other three courses. To test if there is variation in the method of assessment for the four courses, since they were taken at different levels. Analysis of variance tool was used.

The hypothesis is:

H0: $\beta_1 = 0$ (implying that the method of assessment is the same in all the courses)

Vs

HA: $\beta_1 \neq 0$ (implying that the method of assessment is not the same in all the courses)

Using SPSS package, p- value of 0.000 shows that the method of assessment is the same in all the four courses.

ANALYSIS

From the result of the analysis above, it was discovered that the scores of students in the three courses taken at fourth year skewed to the left indicating poor performance. This calls for concern on the part of the teacher who is teaching these courses, to find out where the problem lies and seek for ways of improvement for a better result. Comparing the results at the two different levels, it was discovered that the result at third year is preferable under the same teacher, since it gave a skewness value that is closer to zero. One may think that the teacher's method of assessment/evaluation differs at different level, but the analysis of variance result indicates that method of assessment is the same in all the courses at different levels. Therefore, this calls for the attention of the students on their learning habit. Therefore, this study has shown that evaluation

could be more effective if some fundamental statistics details are also included in the computation of examination results.

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